

Effect of Halide Additives on the Corrosion Behaviour of Lead in Chloroacetic Acid Solutions

E. A. HASSAN, A. S. ABO EL-MAGD, F. H. KAMAL, A. R. EBAID and M. Y. MOURAD

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

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The effect of Cl^- , Br^- and I^- ions on the corrosion behaviour of lead electrodes in aqueous solutions of mono-, di- and tri-chloroacetic acids is evaluated by studying the potential-time and weight-loss measurements. It has been found that the steady-state potentials which obey the relationship $E = a - b \log c$, are shifted towards more negative values with the increase in the concentration of the additive ions.

The decrease in the rate of corrosion with the increase of anion concentration, is probably due to the halide ions acting as anodic inhibitors.

SOME anions promote corrosion while others act as inhibitors. The decision between one or the other behaviour is said to depend on the solubility of the reaction products¹, adsorption², ion size and charge³, ion deformability⁴ and the electrostatic field set up by the negative charge of the anion on adsorption sites⁵. Generally, all anions present in large dilutions are corrosive⁶, but tend to inhibit it in relatively concentrated solutions.

The effect of Cl^- as additive on the cathodic deposition of metals on Hg was investigated⁷. The observed effect of halide ions in decreasing the activation energy was attributed to the formation on the electrode of an intermediate complex ($\text{Cl} - \text{M}^{n+}$), in which the Cl^- acts as an electronic bridge. The retardation of the reaction between HNO_3 and Sn, by iodides of Na and K, is explained⁸ to be due to the specific action of the alkali ions. The inhibition action of NaI, KI and LiI to the reaction accompanied by the formation of thin layer of stannous iodide on the surface of tin, is attributed to the formation of the oxidation products of HI in the reaction mixture.

In the present work, the effect of Cl^- , Br^- and I^- on the corrosion behaviour of lead, is studied in aqueous solutions of mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acids. Steady state potential as a function of both time and concentration of acid containing different anions has been studied. The corrosion rate of lead metal has also been evaluated using the weight-loss procedure.

Experimental

The established steady state potentials of pure lead electrodes were measured in solutions of potassium salts of Cl, Br and I at varying concentrations (10^{-3} - $10^{-1}M$) in 0.1M mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acid solutions.

The lead electrodes used, their preparation and treatment, electrode vessel, procedure and apparatus

for measurements, and the weight-loss technique were the same as reported previously⁹.

Results and Discussion

Potential-time measurements: Potential time curves for lead electrodes in 0.1M mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acid solutions containing Cl^- , Br^- and I^- at concentrations of 10^{-3} to $10^{-1}M$ carried out under open circuit conditions, showed that the steady-state potential values are shifted towards a more negative direction with increasing additive concentration. Such behaviour may be due to the adsorption of halide anions on the metal surface¹⁰.

The negative shift in the values of steady-state potential in presence of Cl^- , Br^- and I^- is higher as compared to the effect of changing the respective concentration of chloroacetic acid solutions, free from halide ions.

Results given in Fig. 1 show the relationship between the molar concentration (c) of halide ion added to 0.1 M solution of the three acids and the values of steady-state potential of lead electrodes. In all cases, the potential decreases with increasing the halide ion concentration. The straight line relationships are found to obey a relation of the type (1).

$$E = a - b \log c \quad (1)$$

where a and b are constants depending on the nature of electrolyte and surface preparation^{6,11}.

The slopes obtained from the linear plots (b values) given in Table 1, show similar relationships as found for steel¹² and zinc¹³ in neutral salt solutions, and cadmium in acid solutions. The decrease in the b values seems to be related to the decrease in aggressiveness of the anion.

Weight-loss measurements: The study of weight-loss measurements in 0.1 M solutions of mono-,

Fig. 1. E. mv. vs log c for lead in mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acids in presence of iodide bromide and chloride.

 TABLE 1—VALUES OF b OBTAINED IN 0.1 M SOLUTION OF MONO-, DI-, AND TRI-CHLOROACETIC ACIDS IN PRESENCE OF Cl^- , Br^- AND I^-

Chloroacetic acid	Values of b in presence of		
	Cl^-	Br^-	I^-
Mono-	-5.2	-10.2	-13.2
Di-	-14.0	-24.0	-24.0
Tri-	-16.0	-30.0	-33.5

are constants depending on the surface preparation of the metal and the nature of solution^{6,11}. The plots of log corrosion rate vs log molar concentration of the acid solutions containing halide ions give straight lines with slopes (b) of 0.275, 0.400 and 0.650 for Cl^- , 0.220, 0.250 and 0.425 for Br^- , and 0.210, 0.115 and 0.125 for I^- in mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acid solutions, respectively (Fig. 2).

The decrease in corrosion rate with the increase of anion concentration suggests that the halide ions act as anodic inhibitors. The inhibitive function of these ions may be associated with their ability to become adsorbed on the metal surface retarding the entry of Pb^{II} ions into the solution at the

Fig. 2. Effect of anion concentration on corrosion rates for lead in 0.1 M solution of mono-, di-, and tri-chloroacetic acids containing halide ions.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF CORROSION RATE WITH ANION (HALIDE) CONCENTRATIONS IN SOLUTIONS OF DIFFERENT CHLOROACETIC ACID

Anion conc. $\times 10^3 M$	Corrosion rate, $\times 10^{-3}$ mg/day/cm ²								
	Cl^-			Br^-			I^-		
	Mono-	Di-	Tri-	Mono-	Di-	Tri-	Mono-	Di-	Tri-
1	1.75	9.94	48.0	0.96	4.80	22.2	0.42	1.20	1.95
5	1.10	5.04	16.8	0.82	3.96	13.8	0.31	0.89	1.77
10	0.91	3.74	15.6	0.62	2.16	7.8	0.25	0.82	1.32
50	—	—	3.6	0.46	—	4.8	—	0.78	1.26
100	0.48	2.50	0.9	0.53	1.44	1.8	0.16	—	1.12

di-, and tri-chloroacetic acids, in presence of Cl^- , Br^- and I^- within concentration range 10^{-3} - $10^{-1} M$, showed that the weight-loss increases linearly with time. The values of corrosion rate calculated from the straight lines, are presented in Table 2. The relationship between the corrosion rate and molar concentration of the acids containing halide ions follows the equation (2).

$$dw/dt = ac^{-b} \quad (2)$$

where dw/dt is the corrosion rate in $\text{mg day}^{-1} \text{dm}^{-2}$; c is the molar concentration, and a and b

anodes. The fact that the double logarithm relation between corrosion rate and salt concentration covers 3-4 orders of magnitude may suggest that the corrosion of lead in halide solutions is controlled by adsorption of anions on the active sites¹⁵.

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